

OUT-OF-PLANE FAILURE MODE ANALYSES OF COMPOSITE T-JOINT

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ABSTRACT

The failure mode of T-shaped angle clip frame to skin joint was analyzed. The T-joint was cut into pull-off specimens and tested under both simply supported and clamped conditions. Four different support spans were used in either simply supported or clamped conditions. Observations of these tests indicate the pull-off specimens' load versus displacement curves remained monotonically increasing as the load increased until an audible cracking sound could be heard accompanied by a slight load drop or deviation from linearity from the load-displacement records. The pull-off specimens then went on to carry additional load after this point. Visual observation of crack or delamination from the specimen' free edges were at a higher load than the one causing the initial load drop. These observations seem to indicate the crack in the adhesive noodle and delamination between the angle clip and the skin first started from the interior of the pull-off specimen. Micrographs of failed specimens were taken from both polished free edges and the polished mid-section from the mid-section cut. The micrographs of the mid-section from all the failed specimens consistently showed crack in the adhesive noodle and delamination between the angle clip and the skin connecting to the crack.

The adhesive noodle crack initiation was analyzed using finite element method. The finite element model was first checked for stiffness prediction against the pull-off specimens' test data in both simply support and clamped conditions. The predictions using published lamina properties for similar carbon fiber material was excellent when compared with test data. The only adjustment to the material properties was to E_{11} to account for fiber volume fraction difference. The stress and strain analyses at the adhesive noodle indicate crack initiation was caused by the maximum principal stress introduced by the maximum bending moment from the pull-off test.

Keywords: Composite angle clip joint, pull-off test, out-of-plane failure mode, delamination

INTRODUCTION

With the increased emphasis on reducing the cost of manufacturing composite structures, secondary bonding or co-curing is an attractive option to eliminate the need for mechanically fastening sub-assemblies. Many composite components in aerospace structures consist of flat or curved panels with co-cured frames and stiffeners. Out-of-plane loading such as internal pressure in a composite fuselage or out-of-plane deformations in a compression loaded post-buckled panel may cause the frame or stiffener to debond from the panel [1]. The out-of-plane failure mode for T-shaped frame to skin joint using angle clips has been studied previously using pull-off tests [2-3].

Pull-off tests results of co-cured joints were analyzed to understand the failure mode and strength of attaching frames and bulkheads to the fuselage skin using angle clips [2-3]. Ref. 2 indicated dependence of pull-off failure load on the support span causing defining pull-off strength in terms of pull-off load problematic. Both two-dimensional and three-dimensional finite element analyses of the

pull-off specimen with existing crack showed delamination between the skin and angle clip starting from this crack will grow dominantly in Mode I opening due to the maximum bending moment at the crack tip [2-3]. Additional pull-off tests were conducted to investigate the support span length effect under either simply support or clamping support conditions [4]. The trend of test data indicates the failure initiation is controlled by the maximum bending moment independent of the support condition and span length [4].

To better understand the failure mode and the trend observed from the test data, specimens tested in Ref. 4 were sectioned and polished to investigate the failed specimens from both free edges and mid sections. All twenty tested specimens were examined under a microscope to see what transpired. In addition, finite element analysis was performed to understand the failure initiation and critical factor governing the crack initiation in the adhesive noodle and connecting back to the critical bending moment test data indicated.

FAILURE MODE INVESTIGATION

The pull-off specimens were cut with diamond-tipped tool from a simple panel made of carbon fiber fabric and infused with the SI-ZG-5A resin system using the VARTM process. The fabrics were intermediate modulus AS4 with 3000 denier in the plain weave (PW) and 6000 denier in the 5-harness satin (5HS) plies. The symmetric skin lay-up was $(\pm 45^{5HS}, 0/90^{PW}, \pm 45^{5HS}, 0/90^{5HS})_s$. The angle clips were made of four plies of the same 5-harness AS4 carbon fabric, all of which were laid-up in $\pm 45^\circ$ orientation. The angle clips were stitched to the skin before infusing.

T-Joint Pull-off Specimen

A schematic drawing of a T-joint pull-off specimen is shown in Figure 1. The pull-off specimen represents a section cut from a frame to skin with angle clip joint. The frame was procured and then co-cured with the skin and angle clips. Typical pull-off specimen width (w) is 50 mm. When testing, the pull-off specimen is supported at both side of the skin and pulled on the frame as shown in Figure 1. A total of twenty pull-off specimens were tested with eight under simply supported condition and twelve under clamped condition as shown in Figure 2 and 3, respectively. The average skin thickness (t_s) and clip flange thickness (t_f) are 2.23 mm and 1.28 mm, while the average skin and clip flange thickness (t_{sf}) is 3.51 mm.

Figure 1 Schematic of T-joint pull-off specimen.

Figure 2 Simply support pull-off specimen test set-up.

Figure 3 Clamped support pull-off specimen test set-up.

Failure Examination

All failed specimens were polished at both free edges to exam the failed specimen cross section under a microscope. In addition, each failed specimen was also cut at the center along the specimen length to observe the inner cross section of the failed specimens.

Roller Supported Test Results

A total of eight specimens were tested under simply supported conditions where two specimens were tested for each of four different spans. The average dimensions and pull-off failure initiation loads for

the eight roller supported specimens are given in Table 1. The failure initiation is defined as the first load drop from the load-displacement curve as shown in Figure 4. The peak load from the initial load drop for each of the eight roller support specimens is included in Table 1 as the initiation load both in terms of the magnitude of the load and in terms of the load divided by the specimen width.

Table 1. Roller support pull-off specimens and their initiation Failure Loads

Specimen ID	Roller Span (mm)	Width w (mm)	Thickness (mm)			Initiation Load	
			t_s	t_{sf}	t_f	P (N)	P/w(N/mm)
101	102	50.9	2.3	3.6	1.3	447	9
102	102	50.8	2.2	3.6	1.4	659	13
121	152	50.8	2.2	3.6	1.4	426	8
122	152	50.8	2.2	3.6	1.4	416	8
111	203	50.8	2.3	3.7	1.4	292	6
112	203	50.8	2.3	3.7	1.4	289	6
131	254	50.8	2.2	3.4	1.2	189	4
132	254	50.8	2.3	3.4	1.1	189	4

Figure 4. Load-displacement curve of specimen 101 under 102 mm span roller support

The first load drop or deviation from linearity is closely associated with the first audible cracking sound as documented in Ref. 4. Visual observation from the edges during the test observed crack and delamination at a later time after the initial cracking sound and at higher load than the peak of the initial load drop. Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude crack and delamination initiation occurred from the interior of the pull-off specimen first and then propagated along the length and width of the

pull-off specimen later. Hence, it is important to also exam the interior section of the pull-off specimen. Micrographs at the adhesive noodle region where failure occurred were taken from both free edges and the mid-section. A set of three photos at these sections for specimen 101 is shown in Figure 5. The mid section micrograph shows a crack leading to the skin and clip flange interface where the delamination initiated. Delamination between the adhesive and skin is visible for all the pictures shown in Figure 5. Similar micrographs at the free edges and mid section for specimen 102 are shown in Figure 6. Crack in the adhesive is observed at the mid section for specimen 102.

Figure 5 Micrographs of failed specimen 101 at both free edges and interior mid section.

Figure 6 Micrographs of failed specimen 102 at both free edges and interior mid section.

Clamped Test Results

The average dimensions and pull-off failure initiation loads for the twelve clamp supported specimens are given in Table 2. There are four different clamp spans with three specimens tested at each of the four spans of 102 mm, 152 mm, 203 mm, and 254 mm. The load-displacement curve for specimen 151 at 102 mm span is shown in Figure 7. Similar to roller supported specimen 101 shown in Figure 4, a noticeable load drop from the linear load-displacement curve can be seen in Figure 7 for clamped specimen 151. This initial load drop is defined as the pull-off initiation load for the clamp support specimens.

Table 2. Clamp support pull-off specimens and their initiation Failure Loads

Specimen ID	Clamp Span (mm)	Width w (mm)	Thickness (mm)			Initiation Load	
			t_s	t_{sf}	t_f	P (N)	P/w(N/mm)
151	102	50.8	2.2	3.4	1.2	919	18
152	102	50.6	2.3	3.4	1.1	920	18
153	102	50.8	2.2	3.4	1.2	757	15
161	152	50.8	2.2	3.4	1.2	612	12
162	152	50.8	2.3	3.5	1.3	711	14
163	152	50.7	2.2	3.5	1.3	657	13
171	203	50.7	2.3	3.5	1.2	580	11
172	203	50.7	2.2	3.6	1.4	537	11
173	203	50.7	2.2	3.5	1.3	527	10
181	254	49.3	2.1	3.4	1.3	390	8
182	254	50.6	2.3	3.6	1.2	580	11
183	254	38.3	2.2	3.5	1.3	319	8

Figure 7 Load-displacement curve of specimen 151 under 102 mm span clamp support.

Micrographs taken from the free edges and mid section for specimens 161, 162 and 163 are shown in Figures 8-10. All the mid section micrographs show the existence of crack leading to the skin and clip flange interface.

Figure 8 Micrographs of failed specimen 161 at both free edges and interior mid section.

Figure 9 Micrographs of failed specimen 162 at both free edges and interior mid section.

Figure 10 Micrographs of failed specimen 163 at both free edges and interior mid section.

FAILURE INITIATION ANALYSIS

A generic pull-off specimen based on nominal lay-up thickness was modeled with two-dimensional finite element to analyze the stresses and strains at the failure location for crack initiation. Both strain and stress parameters were examined to identify the crucial factor governing the crack initiation.

Finite Element Model Description

Due to symmetry, one half of a sample pull-off specimen was modeled with two-dimensional shell elements as shown in Figure 11. The dimensions shown in the figure are in millimeters (mm). The finite element model shown in Figure 11 is a two-dimensional representation of the cross-section of the pull-off specimen. The skin lay-up and angle clip lay-up are $(\pm 45^{5HS}, 0/90^{PW}, \pm 45^{5HS}, 0/90^{5HS})_s$ and $(\pm 45^{5HS})_4$, respectively. The assumed 5HS ply thickness is 0.313 mm, while the assumed PW ply thickness is 0.255 mm. The skin thickness and angle clip thickness are $t_s=2.39$ mm and $t_f=1.25$ mm, respectively.

Smear material properties are used for the two-dimensional shell elements. These two-dimensional smeared properties are derived from classical lamination theory using published three-dimensional lamina properties of $E_{11}=117$ Gpa, $E_{22}=E_{33}=10.3$ Gpa, $G_{12}=G_{23}=G_{31}=7.2$ Gpa, $\nu_{12}=0.27$, $\nu_{23}=0.3$, $\nu_{31}=0.02$, $\alpha_{11}=-0.9 \cdot 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, $\alpha_{22}=\alpha_{33}=27 \cdot 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$ for AS4/3501-6 [5]. Where the modulus $E_{11}=117$ Gpa was reduced from Ref. 5 ($E_{11}=147$ Gpa) to account for the fiber volume fraction difference between the present laminate (52%) and the lamina volume fraction (63%) given in Ref. 5. Each PW and 5HS are considered as two plies with nominal ply thickness of 0.127 mm for PW and 0.157 mm for 5HS.

The resulting two-dimensional material properties for the shell elements are given in Table 6. The material properties for the FM300 adhesive are $E=2.76$ Gpa and $\nu=0.3$.

Figure 11 Two-dimensional finite element model of one half of a pull-off specimen.

Table 3 Smearred properties for 2-D shell elements

Properties	Skin	Blade	Angle Clip	Unit
E_{xx}	44.6	44.6	23.4	Gpa
E_{zz}	11.1	11.1	11.1	Gpa
ν_{xz}	0.21	0.21	0.11	
G_{xz}	7.2	7.2	7.2	Gpa
G_{yz}	7.2	7.2	7.2	Gpa
G_{xy}	19.7	19.7	29.5	Gpa
α_{xx}	1.94	1.94	1.94	$10^{-6}/^{\circ}C$
α_{zz}	33.8	33.8	33.8	$10^{-6}/^{\circ}C$

Figure 12 Stiffness predictions compared with test data for 152 mm span specimens.

The finite element model shown in Figure 11 was used to predict the model stiffness under simply supported and clamped conditions to compare with the test results. The results of the linear finite element analysis and the test results for 152 mm span specimens in both simply and clamped conditions are shown in Figure 12. The straight lines are from the linear finite element analyses for the model shown in Figure 11 under clamped and simply supported conditions. The initial loads recorded at zero displacement as seen in Figures 4 and 7 are removed in Figure 12 to eliminate this artifact in order to better compare with the finite element analysis. The properties introduced in the model seem to represent well the specimen stiffness behaviors in both simply and clamped conditions.

Strain and Stress Analysis

The stresses and strains of interests are in the corner region of the joint (Figures 5-6, 8-10). The idealized detailed finite element model of half of the joint corner is shown in Figure 13 along with the element property regions to represent the local lay-ups and ply orientations. Also appearing in Figure 13 is an enlarged finite element model of the adhesive noodle.

Figure 13 Idealized finite element model at the corner.

The finite element model shown in Figure 13 was analyzed under both simply supported and clamped conditions. Typical stress and strain results for a pull-off specimen under 152 mm span simply supported are provided here to identify the parameter that best describe the crack initiation in the adhesive noodle region. The pull-off load applied (421 N) is the average of the crack initiation loads from specimen 121 (426 N) and specimen 122 (416 N). The distributions of the maximum principal stress and the maximum principal strain are shown in Figure 14. The peak maximum principal stress is seen reaching the adhesive strength near the skin and angle clip interface at start of clip radius where interface delamination is also most likely to occur. On the other hand, the peak maximum principal strain is far from the adhesive's strain capability.

Figure 14 Maximum principal stress and strain at the adhesive noodle.

Figure 15 shows the von Mises strain and the first strain invariant (J_1) at the adhesive noodle. The first strain invariant is mostly negative in the adhesive noodle region indicating J_1 is not applicable to the crack initiation in this region. The peak von Mises strain also does not seem to indicate crack initiation and distortional failure is unlikely in this confined adhesive noodle.

Figure 15 von Mises strain and the first strain invariant (J_1) at the adhesive noodle.

CONCLUSION

Observations of micrographs of tested specimens indicate the failure initiation started from crack initiation in the adhesive noodle adjacent to the region where the angle clip flange curves away from the skin making it also most prone to delamination initiation. Micrographs taken at mid-section from the failed specimens validate the existence of the adhesive noodle crack. The finite element analysis prediction of pull-off specimen stiffness was in good agreement with test data. The maximum principal stress in the adhesive noodle region reaches typical adhesive strength at the average crack initiation load from the pull-off tests. The maximum principal stress is identified to be the controlling factor for crack initiation. The maximum principal stress in the adhesive noodle is a direct effect of the maximum bending moment from the pull-off test.

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